

National Open Access Monitor Advisory Group Meeting, 10th February 2025,
11:30

Minutes

Minutes from meeting 28th June 2024 were approved.

Funding and extension of the National Open Access Monitor

- Susan Informed the group that funding has been received from the HEA to extend the project until the end of 2025
- HEA funding will enable the appointment of a Monitor Project Officer for 12 months. It is expected that this role will be advertised soon
 - A key part of this role will be to work closely with repositories and the engage with the national repository network
 - Clarification is required on remaining unspent NORF funding. IReL had proposed using this to cover hosting and support fees until April 2025
- The group discussed what the Monitor should focus on and prioritise over the coming 12 months.
 - Raise awareness outside of libraries
 - Better integration of the monitor with institutional repositories and those managing repositories. Make it a key consideration when looking at new or updating repository systems (UL could provide a good case study for this).
 - Greater engagement with end users (both those on the ground and senior management), roadshows were suggested to demonstrating case studies and as a useful way of improving the onboarding process
- The Group were asked 'What does Success look like for the Monitor?'
 - Group agreed that there is an appetite for the monitor, it is being used by institutions, but there is real challenge is getting that final 10% of requirements in place, so that data is accurate, and the monitor is fit for purpose and can confidently be used to demonstrate an institution's OA output
 - An important measure of success, will be to see the Monitor regularly used in institutional annual reporting
 - Qualitative and Quantitative measures required – identifying how many people are using the monitor and providing case studies to demonstrate how they are using it
 - **[Action Aaron]** – Aaron to confirm if OpenAIRE can provide user statistics
 - OpenAIRE have proposed expanding the scope of the Monitor to include Books and Open Data. In the near we can look at a National Open Science Monitor
 - The group agreed that a Researcher Dashboard would be a valuable addition to the Monitor

Engagement and Promotion

- Aaron updated the group on monthly webinars which are scheduled by OpenAIRE until the end of April 2025.
- A survey: [Help Shape the Future of the National Open Access Monitor](#) will be conducted this week, seeking feedback from the community
- IReL will submit a proposal for a live Workshop at CONUL 2025, case studies will be presented in addition to an introductory workshop
- Susan noted that she received very positive feedback on the Monitor from international colleagues at the recent OA2020 conference
- Jenny suggested that we could also submit a proposal for a lightning talk at the [TNC25 conference](#)

Next Meeting

- TBC. We will ask OpenAIRE to present an update at this meeting